

THE ROLE OF KAZAKH LEGENDS IN THE LINGUISTIC PICTURE OF THE WORLD

Zakirova A.

*a doctoral student of Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University,
Kazakhstan Republic*

ABSTRACT

Systematization of Kazakh legends, highlighting their differences from other folklore genres, evaluating them from the point of view of the history, criticism, theory of literature were analyzed in this article. The place of legends in the linguistic picture of the world is determined. From the legends considered mainly from the point of view of literary criticism, we have distinguished our object of study, that is, texts analyzed from the point of view of language. Teaching the language of legends should not be limited to conducting a linguistic analysis of the language units used in it. One of the main tasks of the study is the analysis of linguistic and cultural units in legends for the student.

Keywords: worldview, cognitive cognition, a picture of the world, legend, anthropocentrism, linguoculturology, national consciousness, ethnolinguistics.

Introduction. Each nation has its own culture, history, traditions, worldview, and its own values. Although nature and the environment are common for humanity, each people lives in different places and in different ways. Even if a person of any nationality utters the same word, in his mind it can have a different cognitive structure. Despite the fact that each nation understands the elements of a special structure common to all nations in different ways, it creates its own national image and picture of the world. Therefore, a special place in linguistics is occupied by cognitive linguistics, a new direction that studies the relationship between language, culture and the world, their influence on each other.

Relevance of the study. Culture, language, history and society have a great influence on the formation of the picture of the world. Because the language is constantly connected with society, the social environment, the centuries-old history of the people, ethnic knowledge, life experience passed down from generation to generation, spiritual essence, traditions, customs, culture.

Although the knowledge of the human race is the same in all peoples, there are also points that differ when it comes to a separate ethnic group. Throughout life, a person fixes his knowledge in words, while knowing the world. The totality of this knowledge, presented in a linguistic form, is called the linguistic picture of the world. Features of the linguistic picture of the world and its nature depend on language, since language is the most important way of forming a person's knowledge of the world. The linguistic picture of the world reflects not only human ideas about the universe, but also national views on life, traditions, beliefs.

One of the main principles in creating a linguistic picture of the world is the anthropocentric position. In any era, science, education, art, culture – the goal that everyone set for themselves was to get to know a person from the point of view of his experience and values. All various actions in this world are inextricably linked with a person and his personality traits. The importance of studying the anthropocentric in the enumeration of the totality of human knowledge about the whole world is enormous.

Anthropocentricity in linguistics has long been a revelation in the modern scientific community, its facets and secrets are analyzed in detail. The main position of this scientific direction, which has been developing rapidly over the past half century, is to consider language in unity with human existence. Today, on the basis of anthropological linguistics, a number of scientific directions have been formed, interconnected and closely connected with each other. In particular, they are: sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics and paleolinguistics [1]. These disciplines come to life as a result of their sociability and integration with other branches of Science and are considered within the framework of extralinguistics.

Methodology. To identify the factors contributing to the development of the Kazakh legends in the linguistic picture of the world, and to consider the problems in a systematic way. Differentiation in relation to language policy and language strategy based on their sources. Methods of interpretation, intuitive assessment, and linguistic analysis were used.

Discussion and results. Today, one of the only principles that determine the trends in the development of linguistic science is the manifestation of language in an anthropocentric direction. Thus, by studying the language in connection with the ethnic group, its thinking, worldview, common sense, national culture, it creates a linguistic picture of the world. The problem of the linguistic picture of the world in the anthropocentric direction was discussed in Russian linguistics by B.A.Serebrennikov, E.S.Kubryakova, V.I.Postovalova, V.N.Telia, A.A.Ufimtseva, A.Vezhbitskaya, V.G.Kolshansky, Yu.Karaulov, V.Maslov, and in Kazakh linguistics by A.Kaidar, M.Kopylenko, E.Zhanpeisov, K.Khusain, N.Uali the object of research of scientists was B.Kaliev, Zh.Mankeeva, G.Smagulova, G.Sagidolda, A.Islam, B.Tleuberdiev, E.Orazalieva, B.Akberdieva, G.Snasapova, K.Zhamanbayeva, A.Almautova, K.Kurkebayev, A.Amirbekova, G.Tuyakbayev, K.Saryshova, A.Abasilov and others.

Language is the collective name of such spiritual heritage as a text, a work of art, a poem, a fairy tale, a

legend, a proverb, a riddle, a poem, and so on. By studying these heritage, we get to know the person behind it, the nation.

In any language, the worldview, views, consciousness, and personality of the people or nation who speak this language are preserved. For this reason, it is impossible to separate the language from the person, from the nation. Humboldt's statement that "different languages are not different pronunciation of the same thing, but its different expression" [2], "became a grand theory clarifying the relationship between language and nationality. That is, the difference between language and nationality is not just a sign, but a phenomenon that occurs at a much higher, deeper level. Language is formed by speech, and speech is a reflection of thoughts or feelings. The way of thinking and worldview of the people, giving color and character to their language.

If we say a person who creates a linguistic picture of the world, we recognize language through human cognition, communication. So, one of the works of prose folklore arising from the interweaving of language and thinking, National worldview are legends. Legends are unique works based on the experience of life and knowledge of the Kazakh people. The process of knowledge of the ethnic group and the field of perception, study, reasoning, formulation of spiritual values are widely reflected in legends. In the legends, representatives of the previous generation kept their minds and commandments, which they told to the next generation. The most important thing is that the legends have been edited and sorted over hundreds of years of criticism and quickness of the people. Therefore, we can say that folklore, including legends, is a reflection of national artistic thinking and historical consciousness [3].

Academician A.Kaidar "in the language of any ethnic group (today's ulus, people or nation) lies the expression of his whole life. The true essence and worldview of a people, i.e. an ethnic group, are preserved only in its language. The name is the nature of concepts related to tools, weapons, clothing and food, household items and customs, customs, beliefs, game-laughter, feasting, etc., which were necessary in life in every era. Only as facts of language, that is, words and phrases in language, phraseological units and proverbs, legends, fairy tales can reach us" [4]. Therefore, legends are not only a stable and integral part of the centuries-old fund of the Kazakh language, but also the most vivid expression of our national worldview and mentality.

The legends are grouped on different topics, covering all the various events and phenomena of public life, the life of a person, the economic profession, and other various activities, which is undoubtedly one of the main indicators of creating a linguistic picture of the national world through wise reasoning about moral and educational behavior.

There is a concept of a common nation for how many people have formed over the centuries and intertwined in one channel. There will be a national character, national knowledge, national mentality, national psychology that is unique to this nation. The national knowledge of the Kazakh people has been formed and

firmly established over the centuries, so it has a distinctive feature that saves the Kazakh spirit from some shocks. The phenomenon that shows the same quality of our people differs from all material wealth in that it puts human values higher.

Each nation has its own unique rich, treasured history of national knowledge and culture, which has developed over the centuries. Such spiritual heritage of the Kazakh people has been separated from our national knowledge and has become a problem at the state level in recent years. In his article "the course towards the future: modernization of public consciousness", the head of State N.A.Nazarbayev noted that "the very concept of national modernization means the improvement of national consciousness. Our national traditions, language and music, literature, rituals, in short, our national spirit and knowledge should remain in us forever. If the national code and national culture are not observed, there will be no revival..." "I don't know," I said. The national code is national cognition. National knowledge, folk knowledge – the national values, culture and language, religion and mentality, customs, traditions and beliefs of each nation, people, formed over the centuries on the stage of national history.

Folk stereotypes are rather stable ideas about the moral, mental, physical qualities inherent in representatives of different peoples. In the content of folk or national stereotypes, as a rule, orientation opinions about the specified qualities are accumulated. In addition, the content of national stereotypes may contain instructions on how to act in relation to representatives of the same nationality. The national stereotype is closely related to the ethno-cultural stereotype. A national stereotype – contains the national characteristics of a particular people, while ethno-cultural stereotypes-reflect differences in the culture of a particular people.

Conclusion. The vision of any ethnic group about the picture of the world is reflected in the linguistic units used by a member of that ethnic group, in the content of legends from the life and existence of that ethnic group, and it can play the role of a foundation for all cultural stereotypes. Many researchers argue that the linguistic picture of the world is formed with the help of linguocultural units in legends. The analysis of these named linguocultural units helps to understand the originality of the national culture. At the present stage of language development, the sorting analysis of language units and concepts in legends is one of the most pressing tasks of linguoculturology and cognitive linguistics.

References

1. History of Kazakhstan: textbook for the 10th grade of the social and humanitarian direction of a comprehensive school / Tuleubayev A., Kasimbayev Zh., Koigeldiev M. – Almaty: Publishing House "School", 2006. – p.232;
2. Humboldt V. On the development of human languages and communication for the spiritual development of man (1830-1835) // Specific works on language. – Moscow, 1984. – p.400;

3. Tuyakbayev G.A., Abasilov A.M., Saryshova K.S. Historical toponyms of the Syr region. – Astana: Publishing House "Horizon", 2023. – p.292;

4. Kaydar A. Historical lexicology and ethnolinguistics // Problems of historical lexicology of the Kazakh language. – Almaty, 1988. – p.310;

5. Nazarbayev N.A. Orientation to the future: modernization of public consciousness. – Astana, 2017.